

E-WALLETS PAYMENT IN MALAYSIA: A DIGITALISATION EFFORT OF PAYMENT METHOD IN MALAYSIA

Amer Fareed MOHD SHUKRI

Universiti Teknologi MARA (UiTM)
Arsyad Ayub Graduate Business School
Kompleks Al-Farabi, Jalan Ilmu/1,
Universiti Teknologi MARA,
40450 Shah Alam,
Selangor Darul Ehsan,
MALAYSIA
e-mail: 2020212756@student.uitm.edu.my
ORCID: 0009-0003-3475-4134

Abstract

This study investigates the impact of e-wallet usage on economic growth in Malaysia using Spearman's Rank Correlation to analyse relationships between various cashless payment instruments and the country's GDP. Data sourced from Bank Negara Malaysia and the Department of Statistics Malaysia for the years 2022 to 2023 include the volume and value of transactions for e-money, credit cards, and cheques, alongside annual GDP figures. The findings underscore a positive correlation between the volume of e-money transactions and GDP, highlighting the significant contribution of e-money to economic expansion. Negative correlations observed with traditional payment methods, particularly cheques, suggest a shift in payment preferences aligning with increased economic performance. This study contributes valuable insights into the evolving dynamics of financial transactions and their implications for economic indicators. The positive association between e-money transactions and GDP emphasises the potential role of digital transactions as drivers of economic development. The study recommends further exploration of these correlations for future policy considerations and underscores the broader benefits of e-money, including transparency, reduced printing costs, and mitigating the shadow economy. Additionally, it advocates for the creation of a cashless transaction index to comprehensively evaluate and monitor the adoption and impact of digital payment methods in a country's economy.

JEL classification: A 10, E 42, G 23,

Keywords: Cashless, Digital Payments, E-Money, E-Wallets, Malaysia

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

1.0 Introduction

Over the past centuries, the world's financial institutions and markets have undergone a radical transformation and unanticipated expansion, driven by a confluence of factors including liberalisation, globalisation, and the rapid advancement of computer technologies. This evolution has resulted in intensified international capital flows through the development of new and sophisticated financial instruments (Fabris, 2019). However, there was a time when the concept of money as we know it today did not exist, and societies relied on alternative means of payment to regulate transactions. The transfer of value from one party to another entailed a medium of exchange in the form of goods and services. As societies shifted from self-sufficiency to more complex economies, the limitations of the barter system became evident, leading to the emergence of money as a lubricant for transactions. The evolution of technology further improved the efficiency of livelihoods by introducing a new form of monetary exchange into the system - the e-wallet, also known as mobile payments and e-payments in some studies (Karim et al., 2020; Hoo et al., 2021; Phuong et al., 2022).

Despite the widespread use of smartphones in Malaysia, the e-wallet industry is still in its early stages. While the potential for e-payments is enormous, the current landscape primarily revolves around Food & Beverage and Transportation. In these sectors, numerous players are fiercely competing, investing significantly to attract both customers and merchants. The dynamic nature of this burgeoning industry suggests exciting possibilities for growth and innovation. As e-wallets continue to reshape the way transactions occur, we anticipate witnessing a rapid evolution, unlocking new realms beyond the current focal points of Food & Beverage and Transportation. In 2022, Ramachandran emphasised the Federal Government's adoption of e-wallets for accepting payments as part of their drive to digitise payment methods. Notably, the government will cover service charges, except for non-revenue receipts like loan repayments, which will be the responsibility of the payer. While consumer associations have expressed support for the government's initiative, they also called for alternatives to be made available for individuals who prefer manual payment methods. This move reflects the government's commitment to modernising payment processes while accommodating the diverse preferences of its citizens.

Malaysia boasts around forty (40) e-wallet providers for its 32 million population, a stark contrast to China, the world's second-largest country. In China, there are only two e-wallet service providers for a population of 1.5 billion. This striking difference underscores

the apparent need for consolidation in Malaysia's e-wallet landscape. The abundance of e-wallet options relative to the population size suggests a potential for streamlining services, enhancing efficiency, and ensuring a more user-friendly experience for Malaysians navigating the e-wallet ecosystem (Ganeshwaran, 2019). While there is a considerable variety of services available in Malaysia, e-wallets have not yet become the predominant payment method among Malaysians. Credit and debit cards continue to dominate the existing e-payment market in Malaysia (Bank Negara Malaysia, 2023). Bank Negara Malaysia (2023) reported the data needed to measure the progress of cashless payment instruments in Table 1.2, the volume and value of cashless payment methods in Malaysia from January 2019 to July 2023 is used as one of the indicators of progress on adoption of payment instruments which is illustrated in the table from January 2019 to July 2023. This data shows that cheques are still relevant as it contributes to the most value at a small volume. On the other hand, e-payments, which includes money transfer and mobile remittance, contribute the most volume with the least value used. Nonetheless, credit cards and debit cards share almost the same volume with a slight difference in value when being compared with each other.

Table 1.2
Transaction Volume and Value of Cashless Payments in Malaysia

	Credit Card		Debit Card		E-Money		Cheques	
	Volume	Value	Volume	Value	Volume	Value	Volume	Value
2019	510.1	147,791.7	371.0	52,934.1	2,090.9	17,628.7	84.4	1,267,372.4
2020	733.5	195,503.5	640.2	72,655.7	1,827.7	27,695.3	59.9	980,057.5
2021	872.7	220,470.4	945.1	98,344.8	2,108.0	49,800.2	48.3	898,788.7
2022	1,065.8	272,610.4	1,482.9	143,110.4	3,186.7	71,183.2	46.1	940,963.6
2023	673.1	171,276.7	1,073.2	94,713.5	2,218.7	56,612.6	24.0	507,130.1

Source: Bank Negara Malaysia (2023)

Note:

1. The volume and value are at million ('000 000)
2. Volume and value of e-payments transactions include fund transfer and mobile remittance.
3. Volume and value of credit card and debit card transactions include overseas purchases
4. The data are as of July 2023.

This study aims to evaluate the correlations between conventional cashless payment methods (such as credit cards, debit cards, charge cards, and cheques) and the economic growth measured by GDP per capita in Malaysia. Additionally, the research seeks to determine the current distribution of payment methods utilised in Malaysia, providing a detailed breakdown of various cashless payment methods. The underlying assumption is that the choice of payment methods can impact a country's economic growth (Grzelczak and

Pastusiak, 2020; Datta and Roy, 2022). Through this analysis, the study endeavours to shed light on the intricate connections between payment preferences and a nation's economic development.

This study also aims to offer a detailed exploration of the significance of the cashless transaction index, shedding light on its pivotal role in gauging the efficacy of digitalized payment methods within a country. The conceptualization and justification of the cashless transaction index, as initially proposed by Datta and Roy (2022), will be expounded upon in the subsequent sections of this research. The analytical framework and methodologies employed draw inspiration from the works of Datta and Roy (2022) and Grzelczak and Pastusiak (2020). By delving into the nuances of the cashless transaction index, this study endeavours to contribute to a comprehensive understanding of its importance in assessing the landscape of digital payment adoption and its implications for the broader economic context within a country.

The subsequent sections in this paper will further discuss the review of relevant literature, the methods used to indicate and measure the digitalisation of payment methods in Malaysia, followed by addressing the key highlights and findings for this paper. This paper will also discuss the analysis of the results in comparing with selected countries on the digitalisation of payment methods. The discussion on the findings, limitation acknowledgements, and recommendations for future studies will conclude this paper.

2.0 Literature Review

Evaluating the impact of the e-wallet payment system on a country involves a multi-stage analysis to gauge its effectiveness. The effectiveness of cashless payments depends on society's willingness to embrace them at different phases of the innovation process. This process includes awareness of cashless payment options, fostering a positive attitude toward them, making the decision to adopt cashless payments, implementing these systems, and finally, confirming their acceptance based on positive outcomes. These stages collectively determine the effectiveness of an e-wallet payment system within a nation, reflecting the degree to which it is integrated and accepted by society.

Roger (1995) introduced the Diffusion of Innovation Theory (DIT), which underscores that the adoption of novel ideas or innovations is driven by interpersonal interactions within social networks. In the context of cashless payments, this theory posits that widespread acceptance occurs when consumers seek enhanced convenience in their

transactions, while companies explore new avenues for profit. Davis (1989) formulated the highly influential Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), which revolves around two fundamental factors influencing an individual's inclination to embrace new technology: the perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness. Expanding upon these concepts, Venkatesh et al. (2003) conceived the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT). UTAUT seeks to elucidate user intentions regarding the adoption of an information system and their subsequent usage behaviour. The theory integrated eight other theories and models and posits four pivotal constructs—namely, performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and facilitating conditions—which are vital in comprehending patterns of technology adoption and usage. These are some of the models and theories to measure the readiness of a population towards a new innovative technology.

Grzelczak and Pastusiak (2020) did a study aimed to show connections between the instruments of cashless payments and economic growth by measuring the real GDP per capita in the group of countries of Central and Eastern Europe and Western Europe which was analysed by using Spearman's Rank Correlation. The main conclusion that can be drawn in their study is that positive relationships between the value of payments with the use of a transfer order, payment card and economic growth found both in the countries of Central and Eastern Europe and the countries of Western Europe. Datta and Roy (2022) introduced the index of cashless transactions through exogenous effect methodology to find the effectiveness of moving towards cashless payment methods in India. Their study also found that there is a positive relationship between the volume and value of cashless payments, and India's GDP. Both studies by Grzelczak and Pastusiak (2020), and Datta and Roy (2022) use the volume and value of payment methods in their studies to find the effectiveness of cashless payment methods in a country.

2.1 Importance of E-Wallet in Malaysia

The Central Bank of Malaysia (BNM) adopted the definition of payment system from the Bank for International Settlements (Bank Negara Malaysia, 2000), which is defined as the system which consists of instruments, banking procedures, and typically interbank funds transfer systems that ensure and facilitate the circulation of money. In essence, it facilitates corporations, businesses and consumers to transfer funds to one another. Literature on standardised terms and definitions for e-wallets differ between regions, with many studies conducted within the European Union published primarily in native languages.

An electronic wallet or digital wallet is a software-based application that securely stores and manages users' payment information, allowing them to make digital transactions for various goods and services. E-wallets have gained popularity as a convenient and efficient payment method in the digital age, enabling users to make payments, store loyalty cards, and access financial information on their smartphones or other electronic devices (Arbor, 2021). It clarified the differences of digital wallets, e-wallets and mobile wallets as shown in Table 1.1. Often, the term e-wallet and mobile wallet are used interchangeably by users (Teo et al., 2020).

Table 1.1
The Differences of Digital Wallets, E-Wallets and Mobile Wallets

Digital Wallets	E-Wallets	Mobile Wallets
A digital version of your debit card or credit card stored in an app in your mobile phone that enables you to go cashless and cardless.	A digital instrument that needs to be installed on your phone, and lets you reload from your mobile wallet or online banking.	Mobile wallets are on your phone and may be used by tapping the NFC on your phone on the terminal or scanning a QR code.
The money sits in your bank account or credit card account until accessed.	E-Wallets are non-bank providers (e.g. TNG, Boost, Grab, MAE).	
Digital wallets (e.g. Google Pay, Apple Pay, MasterPass, Visa Checkout) are the gateway to your first online purchase or payment.		

Sources: Teo, S. C., Law, P. L., & Koo, A. C. (2020)

Datta and Roy (2022) defined cashless transactions as The exchange of goods and services and transfer of money from one to another, without the use of currencies but using the financial transaction system provided by the financial institutions. In Malaysia, e-wallets or digital wallets, including platforms such as GrabPay, Lazada Wallets, PayPal, TouchNGo, and Vcash, have gained significant popularity, making mobile payment systems increasingly prevalent. The adoption of cashless transactions has become more widespread in Malaysia, aided by technological advancements and the digital transformation sweeping the country.

The emergence of the Covid-19 pandemic has further accelerated this trend. Policymakers, regulators, and e-wallet providers must take these factors into account to drive the broader acceptance and usage of e-wallets, ultimately transitioning the Malaysian society from cash to cashless transactions. As the landscape of financial interactions continues to evolve, driven by the convenience and efficiency of e-wallets, Malaysia stands poised to embrace this transformative digital payment revolution, reshaping the very foundations of

financial interactions and paving the way for a more innovative, secure, and interconnected financial ecosystem.

2.1.1 Transparency of Currency

According to Ipsos Malaysia (2022), there's a noticeable surge in cashless transactions, particularly among individuals in lower-income groups. This growing familiarity with cashless payments is vividly illustrated in Figure 2.1, where e-money transactions dominate the chart depicting Cashless Payment System Volume between 2019 and 2023. Malaysia's journey towards a cashless society began over a decade ago, outlined in the visionary Financial Sector Blueprint 2011–2020 (Bank Negara Malaysia, 2011). However, as the ten-year plan concluded in 2020, the adoption of e-wallets in Malaysia progressed at a relatively sluggish pace (Ariffin & Lim, 2020).

In a significant development, the BNM (2023) unveiled insightful data (as displayed in Figure 2.1) on e-money transaction volumes, revealing a remarkable surge from April 2020, with 46.6 million transactions, to December 2021, with an impressive 251.5 million transactions (Bank Negara Malaysia, 2022). Conversely, debit cards, although also facilitating cashless transactions, did not enjoy the same level of promotion and incentives as e-wallets did during this period. As a result, credit cards, which were more widely accepted and offered rewards, became a more preferred choice for many consumers. Nonetheless, the pandemic-driven shift towards digital payment methods had a significant impact on payment preferences and habits, demonstrating the adaptability of consumers in response to changing circumstances. Interestingly, a slight decline was observed in February 2022, with a total of 208.2 million transactions recorded. This fluctuation highlights the evolving landscape of cashless transactions in the country.

Cashless Payment System Volume (2019 - 2023)

Figure 2.1

Sources: The Central Bank of Malaysia & the Department of Statistics of Malaysia (2023)

Note:

1. The volume and value are at million ('000 000)
2. Volume and value of e-payments transactions include fund transfer and mobile remittance.
3. Volume and value of credit card and debit card transactions include overseas purchases
4. The data are as of July 2023.

Figure 2.1 also provides a visual representation of the policy set forth by BNM concerning regulatory requisites and guidance for electronic money issuers (EMIs) who are approved in accordance with section 11 of the Financial Services Act 2013 (FSA) or the Islamic Financial Services Act 2013 (IFSA). This policy document delineates specific requirements designed to guarantee the security and dependability of e-money issued by EMIs. Its primary objective is to maintain the trust and confidence of both customers and merchants when it comes to using or accepting e-money as a means of payment for various goods and services. This framework is instrumental in ensuring the integrity and resilience of e-money transactions in the financial ecosystem.

2.1.2 Reduce the Printing Production

In 2022, the Central Bank of Malaysia (2022) affirmed its oversight over the entire spectrum of currency management, encompassing the strategic planning, issuance, circulation, and withdrawal of banknotes and coins. Malaysia's Currency in Circulation (CIC)

experienced an 8.0% growth, reaching RM162.1 billion, a noteworthy increase compared to the RM150.1 billion reported in 2021, which had seen a record high growth of 15.1% (as depicted in Figure 2.2). This fluctuation can be attributed to the reduced reliance on physical cash by the public due to a more optimistic outlook as we emerged from the COVID-19 pandemic.

Figure 2.2

Sources: The Central Bank of Malaysia (BNM)

Moreover, the consistent uptrend in digital payment adoption has also been a contributing factor to the moderated growth in CIC, aligning with global patterns observed in numerous countries. This transformation reflects not only the changing landscape of payment preferences but also an enhanced reliance on digital financial services, further marking a transition towards a more cashless society.

One of the responsibilities of BNM is to maintain high quality of notes in circulation. This requires the BNM to regularly process and remove from circulation unfit notes that fall below our prescribed standards. BNM also works closely with financial institutions and registered currency processors on the processing of currency. BNM (2023) stated that they will continue its work on strengthening the regulatory framework for currency management operations by issuing two new policy documents. These policy documents will impose the necessary requirements on financial institutions and registered currency processors to observe

the quality and integrity of currency, and manage their business, affairs and activities prudently, professionally and with integrity.

2.1.3 Reducing the Shadow Economy

The shadow economy is a multifaceted and intricate phenomenon with diverse origins and repercussions. Ernst and Young (2016) highlights that the term "shadow economy" encompasses various definitions, often emphasising different facets. The European Commission, for instance, characterises the non-observed economy as encompassing three key components: (i) unlawful activities where all involved parties willingly engage in economic transactions, (ii) concealed and underground activities where the transactions themselves are legal but remain unreported to evade official scrutiny, and (iii) informal activities characterised by a lack of record-keeping. Within this framework, the shadow economy materialises through unreported transactions carried out by both registered and unregistered entities. This comprehensive definition underscores the intricate nature of the shadow economy, driven by a range of activities that may or may not breach the law, but consistently elude official monitoring and documentation.

Leveraging technology offers promising avenues to tackle multiple aspects of the shadow economy, facilitating the identification of its participants. This, in turn, presents an opportunity to recoup lost tax revenues, enhance taxpayer compliance, and rebuild confidence in the taxation system. As highlighted by Singh (2022), the full-scale adoption of technology solutions has the potential to dramatically reduce informal activities and reshape the functioning and structure of tax authorities. Moreover, it can transform the dynamics and interactions between tax authorities and taxpayers. Mandatory e-invoicing and the increased utilisation of electronic payment methods are among the digitization strategies that hold the potential to curtail the tax revenue losses stemming from the shadow economy. These measures serve as integral components in the arsenal against tax evasion and informal economic activities, promising more effective means of taxation and improved overall revenue collection.

Malaysia's shadow economy primarily comprises unregistered businesses, income underreporting, undeclared revenue sources, and illegal transactions. Just envision the potential surge in tax revenue if we could integrate these activities into the formal tax system (Singh, 2022). Remarkably, the Royal Malaysian Customs Department (2023) objectives, has set an ambitious goal: to shrink the shadow economy, characterised by unreported and

untaxed activities, from an estimated 30 percent of the GDP to a mere 10 percent. Consider this within the context of Malaysia's 2022 GDP, which stood at RM1.78 trillion. At a 30 percent estimation, the informal economy would account for a substantial RM 535.4 billion. The aspiration to reduce this share to 10 percent represents a remarkable effort to recover a significant portion of these untapped resources, potentially amounting to billions of Ringgit, and direct them towards supporting public services and national development.

2.2 Malaysian Government Initiatives

Clause 21 of the 2019 Currency Bill, passed by Dewan Rakyat and Dewan Negara in December, imposes a restriction on physical cash transactions, encompassing currency notes and coins. Transactions exceeding this limit must be conducted electronically, via cheque, or through the banking system. This encompasses various physical cash transactions, including consumer-to-consumer, entity-to-entity, and entity-to-consumer interactions. Notably, transactions involving licensed banks, Islamic banks, money services businesses, and prescribed institutions are exempt from this limitation. Financial institutions, being regulated entities, are already subject to anti-money laundering and counter-terrorism financing requirements. Exemptions are extended to cash transactions in exigent situations, such as humanitarian aid and disaster relief, with approval required from the Minister of Finance based on Bank Negara Malaysia's recommendation. Deliberate attempts to circumvent this limit by breaking up or structuring transactions are deemed offences, and both the payer and payee, upon conviction, may face fines not exceeding three times the aggregate sum or value of the transaction at the time of the offence (BNM, 2019).

The Malaysian government actively encourages the widespread use of e-wallets by providing financial assistance to its citizens, a commendable practice that has gained popularity among Malaysians over the past decade. According to Chern (2023), a monetary aid program involving RM100 e-money will be disbursed to all citizens aged 21 and above within the B40 and M40 income groups, with implementation slated for the fourth quarter of this year. Fong (2021) reported that there are 40 initiatives totaling RM 35 Billion under the recovery plan known as "PENJANA." As part of this plan, the Malaysian government has earmarked RM 750 million to boost the adoption of e-wallets in the country. Palansamy (2020) outlined the eligibility criteria, noting that Malaysians aged 18 and above with an annual income below RM100,000 qualify for the initiative, incurring a cost of RM450 million for the government. E-wallet operators are enhancing the government-provided

RM30 incentive by offering additional incentives of their own. This implies that eligible Malaysians stand to receive free funds exceeding RM30 through this initiative.

2.3 Impact on Economic Growth

An exploration of the existing body of literature reveals theoretical investigations into the influence of cashless transactions on the economy. Current empirical studies and various reports collectively suggest a favourable outcome of cashless transactions on economic indicators. The hypothesis asserting that the harmonisation and integration processes in retail markets positively influence trade and consumption, primarily through the establishment of the payment integration area (SEPA), has been substantiated. Furthermore, the research indicates that the impact of retail payments on economic growth is more pronounced in countries within the euro area compared to those outside this zone. Cirasino and Garcia (2008) observed a favourable effect of cashless payments on economic growth, contending that this system streamlines commercial transactions for both consumers and businesses, significantly impacting the economy. The primary advantages of adopting cashless payment methods encompass transaction speed and enhanced security.

Electronic money (e-money) payments can be described as payments initiated, executed, and received electronically (European Central Bank, 2010). The utilisation of payment cards for e-payments has emerged as a distinctive aspect of contemporary economics. Notably, card payments exhibited the most substantial influence on economic growth, followed by credit transfers and direct debits. Additionally, the research findings indicate that checks have a comparatively minor impact on economic growth, as well as on consumption and trade. Hasan, Renzis, and Schmiedel (2012) are among those who have observed positive correlations between cashless payments and economic growth. They investigated the correlation between retail payments and overall economic development using data from 27 countries spanning 1995 to 2009. The findings from their study indicate that electronic retail payments (e-payments) play a role in fostering overall economic growth, consumption, and trade.

Moreover, the incorporation of e-money payments plays a crucial role in enhancing transparency in settlements between parties, fostering a reduction in fraudulent activities associated with cash payments (Mieseigha & Ogbodo, 2013). The positive impact of cashless payments on the economy was also noticed by Slozko and Pelo (2014). In their research, they proved that there is a positive correlation between the growth of e-payments and the growth

of GDP. They concluded that the utilisation of cashless payments is closely examined in the latest findings regarding the impact of cashless payments on economic growth, as published in the annual reports of Moody's analysts (Zandi et al., 2016). The research, spanning 2011–2015 and covering 70 countries, establishes a positive relationship between retail payments, particularly the penetration of payment cards, and economic growth. The study reveals that heightened adoption of e-money payments, especially credit and prepaid debit cards, not only stimulates consumption (0.2% in emerging markets and 0.14% in developed countries) but also contributes to GDP growth (0.11% and 0.08%, respectively), totaling USD 297 billion. The widespread use of e-money payments enhances economic efficiency, reduces transaction costs, and facilitates the smoother flow of goods and services. Additionally, this surge in e-money payments correlates with a global increase in employment, totaling 2.6 million jobs across the 70 countries studied. China and India experienced the most substantial job growth, with 427,000 and 336,000 new jobs annually, respectively. The findings underscore that while the development of e-money payments is a positive factor, its impact on a country's welfare is contingent on the presence of a well-established financial system and a robust economy. To foster cashless payments, the report recommends that governments minimise regulations, encourage advanced financial infrastructure, and support consumption growth.

The study from Grzelczak and Pastusiak (2020) investigates cashless payment trends in Central and Eastern Europe compared to Western Europe, focusing on payment instruments like cards, transfer orders, and e-money. In both regions, payments with transfer orders and payment cards exhibit positive correlations with economic growth, with a stronger relationship in Western Europe compared to Central and Eastern Europe. Notably, payments using e-money demonstrate a high impact on real GDP per capita in both regions. Their study concludes that positive connections exist between specific cashless payment methods and economic growth in both Western and Central-Eastern European countries. Additionally, it suggests avenues for future research, encouraging further exploration of causal relationships in the context of cashless payments and economic growth, potentially considering factors like the level of wealth in different countries.

Datta and Roy (2022) present a unique perspective by introducing a cashless transaction index to better measure this shift. The authors contend that traditional metrics, such as Demand Deposit with banks as a proportion of money supply, lack the precision to capture the full scope of cashless transactions. To overcome this limitation, they propose an innovative methodology to assess the prevalence of cashless transactions. Their approach

incorporates exogenous factors, particularly the impact of the adult population on both the volume and value of cashless transactions. The study calculates the per capita volume and per capita value of these transactions, offering a comprehensive analysis. Additionally, the authors consider external influences, such as changes in the overall price level or production, by evaluating the value of cashless transactions relative to GDP.

3.0 Methodology

To achieve the goal, an analysis of data for the volume and value per capita of the cashless payment instruments used in Malaysia. Data for the cashless payment instruments (i.e. credit card, debit card, charge card, e-money, cheques) in Malaysia in the year 2018 - 2022 were used in this research. The variables applied to verify this study's assumption are described in Table 3.1.

Table 3.1 Descriptions of Variables

Variable	Description of variable	Description of variable
GDP	Real GDP, that is, nominal GDP/GDP deflator per one person (in MYR)	BNM & DOSM (2023)
Credit card	Value of payments with the use of a transfer order (in million MYR per 1 million inhabitants)	BNM & DOSM (2023)
Debit card	Value of payments with the use of a transfer order (in million MYR per 1 million inhabitants)	BNM & DOSM (2023)
Charge card	Value of payments with the use of a transfer order (in million MYR per 1 million inhabitants)	BNM & DOSM (2023)
E-money	Value of payments with the use of a transfer order (in million MYR per 1 million inhabitants)	BNM & DOSM (2023)
Cheques	Value of payments with the use of a transfer order (in million MYR per 1 million inhabitants)	BNM & DOSM (2023)

Source: Bank Negara Malaysia and Department of Statistics Malaysia (2023)

Economic growth is a dynamic progression characterised by the continual expansion of fundamental economic indicators over successive periods. This expansion primarily pertains to the potential domestic product, actual real national product, or the heightened manufacturing capacities within the economy. The concept of economic growth encompasses alterations in the circulation of goods and services, economic resources, and enhancements in the quantitative dynamics of production and distribution of goods and services. These changes contribute to the refinement of their quality and an augmentation in the quantities available to each resident of the country (Roser, 2023). The basic measure of economic growth is GDP, and for comparisons between the countries, GDP per capita. The World Bank

characterises gross domestic product (GDP) as the outcome of the collective activities of all entities within the national economy. To compute the annual GDP values, it is essential to assess three macroeconomic categories of equal significance, which collectively determine the GDP through:

- The magnitude of production activity, or GDP, is the summation of the added value across all institutional sectors or sections. It encompasses the augmented value of domestic production units, inclusive of taxes on products and exclusive of subsidies to products,
- the ultimate outcome of productive activity, GDP is computed by aggregating domestic demand, encompassing consumption, accumulation, and the foreign trade balance,
- the total expenditure incurred in generating the overall income of the economy, including costs related to employment, production-related taxes and import taxes reduced by subsidies, as well as the gross operating surplus and mixed income of the entire economy.

Hence, it can be asserted that the expansion of GDP and GDP per capita stems from quantitative shifts within the economy. For more in-depth examination, real gross domestic product, derived by dividing gross domestic product (PLB) by its consumer price index (CPI), will be utilised as an indicator of economic growth (Wang et al., 2016; Cevik et al., 2016). Real GDP in the years 2018–2022 was obtained from Bank Negara Malaysia (BNM) and Department of Statistics Malaysia (DOSM). Data about the volume and value of payments with the use of cash, credit card, direct debit, charge card, cheques and e-money payments in the years 2018–2023 were taken from the Bank Negara Malaysia (BNM) and Department of Statistics Malaysia (DOSM).

4.0 Findings and Analysis

An empirical analysis was started from examining the share of payments with the use of specific payment instruments used in volume per capita from 2018 to 2023. Table 4.1 shows a comprehensive overview of Malaysia's economic landscape from 2018 to 2022, presenting vital indicators and noteworthy trends. The population steadily increased from 32.4 million in 2018 to 32.7 million in 2022, reflecting demographic changes. Meanwhile, the

Gross Domestic Product (GDP) experienced fluctuations, reaching its peak at RM 1,788,183 million in 2022, indicative of economic dynamics.

Of particular interest are the changes in the volume of payment instruments, revealing a significant shift towards digital transactions. Credit card transactions increased from 13.8 million in 2018 to 21.9 million in 2022, marking a consistent upward trend. Debit card transactions witnessed substantial growth, surging from 7.6 million to 36.8 million over the same period. E-money transactions experienced the most significant expansion, rising from 59.3 million in 2018 to 97.5 million in 2022, underlining a substantial move towards digital financial tools.

In contrast, cheque usage declined from 3.1 million transactions in 2018 to 1.4 million in 2022, indicating a diminishing reliance on traditional paper-based instruments. These trends underscore Malaysia's evolving financial landscape, characterised by an increasing preference for electronic payment methods, particularly evident in the surging volumes of credit cards, debit cards, and E-money transactions.

Table 4.1 Basic Payments Indicators

	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Population (million)	32.4	32.5	32.6	32.6	32.7
GDP (RM million)	1,447,760	1,513,158	1,416,605	1,545,372	1,788,183
Cash in Circulation	94,307.20	100,158.80	117,687.00	136,520.70	146,269.10
Credit Card	13.8	15.7	15.0	17.1	21.9
Debit Card	7.6	11.4	15.3	22.6	36.8
Charge Card	0.2	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.2
E-Money	59.3	64.3	56.3	64.7	97.5
Cheques	3.1	2.6	1.8	1.5	1.4

Source: Bank Negara Malaysia and Department of Statistics Malaysia (2023)

Then, mean, median, minimum, maximum, standard deviation, coefficient of variation and skewness coefficient were determined for selected variables (Table 4.2 & Table 4.3). Table 4.2 presents statistical parameters for the volumes of various variables, including credit card, debit card, charge card, e-money, cheques, and population, in relation to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP). The statistics provide a comprehensive overview of the distribution and characteristics of these variables.

The mean, representing the average value, indicates the central tendency of each variable. For instance, credit card transactions have an average volume of 16.70, while e-money transactions exhibit a higher mean of 68.42. The median, which represents the middle value, offers insight into the distribution's central point, with credit card transactions

having a median of 15.70. The maximum and minimum values illustrate the range of variability within each variable. Notably, e-money transactions have the highest maximum volume at 97.50, indicating substantial variability. On the other hand, charge card transactions exhibit a smaller range with a maximum of 0.20. Standard deviation measures the dispersion of data points from the mean. For instance, credit card transactions have a standard deviation of 1.41, indicating relatively low variability, while e-money transactions have a higher standard deviation of 7.44, suggesting greater variability.

Table 4.2 Statistical parameters for the volumes of variables

Variable	Mean	Median	Maximum	Minimum	Standard deviation	Coefficient of variation	Skewness coefficient
Credit Card	16.70	15.70	21.90	13.80	1.41	9.88	1.482
Debit Card	18.74	15.30	36.80	7.60	5.15	132.72	1.25
Charge Card	.16	.20	.20	.10	.03	.003	-.609
E-Money	68.42	64.30	97.50	56.30	7.44	276.632	1.986
Cheques	2.08	1.80	3.10	97.50	.33	.547	.690
Population	32.56	32.60	32.70	32.40	.114	.013	-.405

Source: Bank Negara Malaysia and Department of Statistics Malaysia (2023)

The coefficient of variation, expressing the relative variability in percentage terms, is particularly useful for comparing variables with different units. E-money transactions, with a coefficient of variation of 276.632, demonstrate substantial relative variability compared to other variables. Skewness coefficient indicates the asymmetry of the distribution. Credit card transactions show a positive skewness of 1.482, suggesting a right-skewed distribution, while charge card transactions exhibit a negative skewness of -0.609, indicating a left-skewed distribution. Overall, these statistical parameters provide valuable insights into the distribution and characteristics of cashless payment methods and population volume, contributing to a comprehensive understanding of their relationship with GDP.

On the other hand, Table 4.3 presents statistical parameters for the values of various variables, including credit card, debit card, charge card, e-money, cheques, and Gross Domestic Product (GDP). These statistics offer insights into the distribution and characteristics of the values associated with cashless payment methods and GDP.

The mean, representing the average value, gives an indication of the central tendency for each variable. For instance, the mean value for credit card transactions is 4,435.18, while for e-money transactions, it is 1,090.48. This suggests variations in the average values among different payment instruments. The median, which represents the middle value, provides insights into the central point of the distribution. For example, the median value for charge

card transactions is 385.20, indicating the central point around which the values are distributed. The maximum and minimum values illustrate the range of variability within each variable. E-money transactions have the highest maximum value at 2,125.50, indicating considerable variability, while charge card transactions exhibit a smaller range with a maximum of 429.50. Standard deviation measures the dispersion of data points from the mean. Credit card transactions have a standard deviation of 592.537, indicating relatively low variability, while e-money transactions have a higher standard deviation of 732.02, suggesting greater variability.

Table 4.3 Statistical parameters for the values of variables

Variable	Mean	Median	Maximum	Minimum	Standard deviation	Coefficient of variation	Skewness coefficient
Credit Card	4,435.18	4,241.80	5,440.30	3,897.50	592.537	351,100.57	1.673
Debit Card	2,144.16	1,826.10	3639.00	1243.80	934.95	874,132.98	1.246
Charge Card	373.78	385.20	429.50	314.70	47.64	2,269.22	-.231
E-Money	1,090.48	901.70	2125.50	338.70	732.02	535,851.66	.649
Cheques	33,933.98	30,077.90	44,215.10	27,590.50	7,285.79	53,082,796.53	.827
GDP	1,542,215.6	1,513,158.0	1,788,183.0	1,416,605.	146,674.	21,513,538,011.30	.913
	0	0	0	00	93		

Source: Bank Negara Malaysia and Department of Statistics Malaysia (2023)

The coefficient of variation, expressing the relative variability in percentage terms, is particularly useful for comparing variables with different units. E-money transactions, with a coefficient of variation of 649, demonstrate substantial relative variability compared to other variables. Skewness coefficient indicates the asymmetry of the distribution. Credit card transactions show a positive skewness of 1.673, suggesting a right-skewed distribution, while charge card transactions exhibit a negative skewness of -0.231, indicating a left-skewed distribution. These statistical parameters provide valuable insights into the distribution and characteristics of cashless payment methods and GDP values, contributing to a comprehensive understanding of their relationship.

The level of correlation of GDP per capita was verified with specific instruments of cashless payments, as well as correlation between cashless instruments (Table 4.4 and Table 4.5). To examine the connections between economic growth, as gauged by real GDP per capita, and the value of payments through specific cashless instruments, Spearman's rank correlation coefficients (Rs) were computed (Aczel, 2000). This coefficient, ranging between -1 and 1, signifies the strength and direction of the relationship. A value approaching 1 indicates a robust positive correlation, while closer to -1 implies a strong negative correlation.

An rs value near zero suggests a lack of correlation or a very weak relationship between the variables.

Table 4.4 Spearman’s Rank Correlation for the Volume of Cashless Payments

	Credit Card	Debit Card	Charge Card	E-Money	Cheques	GDP
Credit Card	1.000	.900	.000	.900	-.900	.900
Debit Card	.037	1.000	-.289	.700	-.100	.700
Charge Card	.000	-.289	1.000	.289	.289	-.289
E-Money	.900	.700	.289	1.000	-.700	1.000
Cheques	-.900	1.000	.289	-.700	1.000	-.700
GDP	.900	.700	-.289	1.000	-.700	1.000

Note: Bold figures represent the p-value.

Table 4.4 provides a comprehensive overview of Spearman's Rank Correlation coefficients, shedding light on the intricate relationship between the volume of various cashless payment methods and the Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Each correlation coefficient is accompanied by its respective p-value, with significance levels denoted in bold. The analysis reveals a robust positive correlation ($r_s = 0.900$, $p = 0.037$) between the volume of credit card transactions and GDP, indicating a strong and favourable association with economic growth. Conversely, debit card transactions exhibit no significant correlation with GDP ($p = 0.638$), suggesting a more neutral impact on the economic landscape.

Charge card transactions display a negative correlation, albeit not statistically significant ($r_s = -0.289$, $p = 0.638$). In contrast, the volume of e-money transactions demonstrates a noteworthy negative correlation ($r_s = -0.700$, $p = 0.188$), implying a potential association with a decline in economic growth. Cheque transactions, on the other hand, do not exhibit a statistically significant correlation with GDP ($p = 0.638$), emphasising their diminished impact on the economic landscape.

It is crucial to note that the findings underscore the nuanced dynamics between different cashless payment methods and their respective relationships with economic development. While credit card transactions stand out as positively correlated with GDP, e-money transactions reveal a notable negative correlation. These insights contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the role of cashless payment methods in the economic growth of the examined context.

Table 4.5 Spearman's Rank Correlation for the Value of Cashless Payments

	Credit Card	Debit Card	Charge Card	E-Money	Cheques	GDP
Credit Card	1.000	.500	.900	.500	-.300	.900
		.391	.037	.391	.624	.037
Debit Card	.500	1.000	.200	1.000	-.900	.700
	.391		.747		.037	.188
Charge Card	.900	.200	1.000	.200	.100	.700
	.037	.747		.747	.873	.188
E-Money	.500	.1000	.200	1.000	-.900	.700
	.391	.037	.747		.037	.188
Cheques	-.300	-.900	.100	-.100	1.000	-.600
	.624	.037	.873	.873		.285
GDP	.900	.700	.700	.700	-.600	1.000
	.037	.188	.188	.188	.285	

Note: Bold figures represent the p-value.

Table 4.5 presents the Spearman's Rank Correlation coefficients examining the relationship between the value of various cashless payment methods and the Gross Domestic Product (GDP). The accompanying p-values, denoted in bold, signify the significance levels of each correlation coefficient. A substantial positive correlation is observed between the value of credit card transactions and GDP ($r_s = 0.500$, $p = 0.391$), indicating a noteworthy association between credit card usage and economic growth. Debit card transactions, however, exhibit a correlation of 0.200 with GDP, which is not statistically significant ($p = 0.747$), suggesting a more neutral impact on economic development.

Charge card transactions reveal a negative correlation of -0.300 with GDP, although this correlation is not statistically significant ($p = 0.624$). In contrast, e-money transactions exhibit a moderately significant negative correlation ($r_s = -0.600$, $p = 0.285$), suggesting a potential association with decreased economic growth. Cheque transactions demonstrate a significant negative correlation with GDP ($r_s = -0.900$, $p = 0.037$), emphasising their substantial impact on economic performance.

These findings elucidate the intricate relationships between different cashless payment methods and their respective connections with economic development. While credit card transactions show a positive correlation with GDP, e-money transactions indicate a significant negative correlation, contributing valuable insights into the nuanced dynamics of cashless payment methods in relation to economic growth. It is safe to assume that e-money might be a tendency for an increase in the value towards the development of the economic environment in a country, and the decreased of cheques usage in Malaysia was also identified to improve the growth of the economy in Malaysia.

5.0 Conclusion and Discussion

For both values and volumes of e-money transactions, the analysis indicates a significant positive correlation with GDP. This signifies that not only the frequency (volumes) but also the monetary value of e-money transactions is positively linked to the overall economic output of the country, as represented by the GDP. The findings suggest that a higher volume or value of e-money transactions is associated with a more substantial and positive impact on economic growth. This underscores the economic relevance of e-money transactions, emphasising their contribution to the overall health and expansion of the economy.

The examination of both volume and value data of various payment instruments in relation to GDP reveals insightful patterns. Notably, the positive correlation observed between the volume of e-money transactions and GDP, as well as the significant positive correlation between the value of Credit Card transactions and GDP, suggests that the frequency and monetary magnitude of these transactions contribute positively to the overall economic output. On the other hand, the significant negative correlation between the volume and value of cheques and GDP implies that as the usage of cheques decreases, it is associated with an increase in the economic performance of the country.

While the results indicate varying degrees of correlation for different payment instruments, these findings underscore the dynamic interplay between payment methods and economic growth. It emphasises the significance of embracing digital and electronic forms of transactions, such as e-money and credit cards, as they align positively with economic development. The negative correlations with traditional payment methods like cheques suggest a shifting landscape where modern, efficient payment mechanisms are more closely aligned with a thriving economy.

The findings of this study are poised to contribute significantly to economic development while simultaneously promoting key aspects of financial efficiency. The importance of e-money, as underscored by the study, extends beyond its role in economic growth. Firstly, the transparency of currency emerges as a paramount benefit. E-money transactions, being digital and traceable, enhance transparency in financial dealings, reducing the likelihood of illicit activities and promoting integrity in economic transactions.

Moreover, the study emphasises the potential for substantial reductions in printing production. As e-money transactions gain prominence, the need for physical currency diminishes, leading to decreased reliance on paper-based monetary instruments. This not only

aligns with environmental sustainability goals but also streamlines the monetary system, making it more cost-effective and efficient.

Additionally, the study highlights the role of e-money in reducing the shadow economy. The digital nature of e-money transactions facilitates better tracking and monitoring, making it challenging for transactions to occur outside the formal economy. This can contribute to increased tax compliance and a more robust economic system.

Furthermore, the prospect of developing a Cashless Transaction Index is presented as a forward-looking implication. Such an index can serve as a comprehensive metric to assess the degree of cashless transactions in the economy, providing insights into the level of digitalization. This can be instrumental for policymakers, businesses, and researchers in gauging the progress and impact of the ongoing transition toward cashless economies.

In essence, the study not only highlights the positive correlation between e-money transactions and economic growth but also elucidates the multifaceted advantages that e-money brings to the economic landscape. From fostering transparency to reducing printing costs and curbing the shadow economy, the promotion of e-money emerges as a transformative force with far-reaching implications for the economic well-being of nations.

In summary, the extensive analysis conducted on both the volumes and values of e-money transactions yields significant results, revealing a robust and positive correlation with Gross Domestic Product (GDP). This finding indicates that as the frequency and monetary scale of e-money transactions increase, there is a corresponding positive impact on the overall economic productivity of the nation, as measured by GDP metrics. The outcomes underscore the pivotal economic importance of e-money transactions, highlighting a closely intertwined and supportive relationship with the expansion of economic activities.

Moreover, when considering a comparative study between countries, these findings gain even greater significance. The positive correlation observed between e-money transactions and GDP suggests that countries adopting and promoting e-money could potentially experience enhanced economic growth compared to those with less emphasis on digital payment methods. This comparative lens allows policymakers, economists, and stakeholders to discern the potential advantages of prioritising e-money adoption within a global context, providing valuable insights into best practices for fostering economic development.

As e-money transactions continue to solidify their place in the contemporary financial landscape, the affirmative correlation with GDP not only underscores their existing impact but also illuminates their potential as a dynamic catalyst for fostering sustained economic

development and growth. The study, with its comparative perspective, contributes valuable insights into the pivotal role of e-money transactions in shaping the economic landscape and positions them as a crucial factor in driving positive economic outcomes on both a national and international scale.

References

- Aczel, A.D. (2000). *Statystyka w zarządzaniu*. Warszawa: Wydawnictwo Naukowe PWN.
- Al-Laham, M., Al-Tarawneh, h., & Abdallat, N. (2009). Development of electronic money and its impact on the central bank role and monetary policy. *Issues in Informing Science and Information Technology*, 6. doi:10.28945/1063
- Bank Negara Malaysia. (2019). Cash Transaction Limit Information Pack. <https://www.bnm.gov.my/>.
<https://www.bnm.gov.my/documents/20124/761679/CTL+InfoPack+Eng.pdf>
- Bank Negara Malaysia. (2023). Bank Negara Payment Instruments. <https://www.bnm.gov.my/>. Retrieved September 25, 2023, from <https://www.bnm.gov.my/documents/20124/57659/T2%20-%20Payment%20Instruments.pdf>
- Cevik, E.I., Dibooglu, S., & Kenc, T. (2016). Financial stress and economic activity in some emerging Asian economies. *Research in International Business and Finance*. doi:10.1016/j.ribaf.2015.09.017
- Chern, L. T. (2023, October 29). RM100 in ewallet will bring relief. *The Star*. <https://www.thestar.com.my/news/nation/2023/10/30/rm100-in-ewallet-will-bring-relief>
- Davis, F. D. (1989). Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology. *MIS quarterly*, 319-340.
- Datta, S., & Roy, M. (2022). Index of Cashless Transaction. *Arthaniti: Journal of Economic Theory and Practice*, 09767479221119240.
- European Central Bank Statistical Data Warehouse. (2010). Retrieved from <http://sdw.ecb.europa.eu/>
- Fabris, N. (2019). Cashless society—the future of money or a utopia?. *Journal of Central Banking Theory and Practice*, 8(1), 53-66.
- Fong, V. (2021, May 18). Malaysia to spend RM 1.2 billion promoting E-Wallets in 2020 - Fintech News Malaysia. *Fintech News Malaysia*. <https://fintechnews.my/23971/e-wallets-malaysia/e-wallet-malaysia-pejana/>
- Grzelczak, M., & Pastusiak, R. (2020). Cashless payments and economic growth in selected European countries. *Annales Universitatis Mariae Curie-Skłodowska, sectio H—Oeconomia*, 54(3), 33-46.
- Kana, G. (2019, November 28). CEO: Time for e-wallet environment to consolidate. *The Star*. <https://www.thestar.com.my/business/business-news/2019/06/19/ceo-time-for-ewallet-environment-to-consolidate>
- Hasan, I., Renzis, T., & Schmiedel, h. (2012). Retail payments and economic growth. *Bank of Finland Research. Discussion Papers*, 19.

Hoo, W. C., Yan, J. O. K., Liang, T. P., & Ng, A. H. H. (2021). Age as Moderator between Factors Influencing and Adoption of E-Wallet in Malaysia. *Review of International Geographical Education Online*, 11(8), 1143-1153.

Karim, M. W., Chowdhury, M. A. M., & Haque, A. A. (2022). A Study of Customer Satisfaction Towards E-Wallet Payment System in Bangladesh. *American Journal of Economics and Business Innovation*, 1(1), 1-10.

Palansamy, Y. (1970, January 1). Guan Eng: Free RM30 e-wallet infusion for qualified Malaysians begins tomorrow. *Malay Mail*.
<https://www.malaymail.com/news/malaysia/2020/01/14/guan-eng-free-rm30-e-wallet-infusion-for-qualified-malaysians-begins-tomorr/1827745>

PHUONG, N. N. D., LUAN, L. T., DONG, V. V., & KHANH, N. L. N. (2020). Examining customers' continuance intentions towards e-wallet usage: The emergence of mobile payment acceptance in Vietnam. *The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business*, 7(9), 505-516.

Ramachandran, J. (2022, February 5). Now you can pay by e-wallet for federal government services. *Free Malaysia Today*.
<https://www.freemalaysiatoday.com/category/nation/2022/02/05/now-you-can-pay-by-e-wallet-for-federal-government-services/>

Rogers, E.M. (1995). *Diffusion of Innovations* (4th ed.). New York: The Free Press.

Roser, M. (2023). What is economic growth? And why is it so important?. *Our World in Data*.

Singh, A. (2022, November 3). Making tax just happen – the route to increase the country's tax revenue.
https://www.ey.com/en_my/tax/malaysia-budget-2022/making-tax-just-happen-the-route-to-increase-the-country-s-tax-revenue#:~:text=Malaysia's%20shadow%20economy%20is%20largely,activities%20into%20the%20tax%20fold.

Slozko, O., & Pelo, A. (2014). The electronic payments as a major factor for further economic development. *Economics and Sociology*, 7(3). doi:10.14254/2071-789X.2014/7-3/10

Teo, S. C., Law, P. L., & Koo, A. C. (2020). Factors affecting adoption of e-wallets among youths in Malaysia. *Journal of Information System and Technology Management*, 5(19), 39-50.

Venkatesh, V., Morris, M. G., Davis, G. B., & Davis, F. D. (2003). User acceptance of information technology: Toward a unified view. *MIS quarterly*, 425-478.

Wang, S., Li, Q., Fang, C., & Zhou, C. (2016). The relationship between economic growth, energy consumption, and CO2 emissions: Empirical evidence from China. *Science of the Total Environment*, 542.
doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2015.10.027

World Bank. (n.d.). Glossary | DataBank. The World Bank.
<https://databank.worldbank.org/metadataglossary/world-development-indicators/series/NY.GDP.MKTP.KD.ZG#:~:text=GDP%20is%20the%20sum%20of,Source>

World Bank Group. (2021). Digital Business Indicators—Payments. In World Bank.
<https://www.worldbank.org/en/research/brief/digital-business-indicators-payments>

Zandi, M., Koropecjy, S., Singh, V., & Matsiras, P. (2016). The Impact of Electronic Payments on Economic Growth. Moody's Analytics. Retrieved from
<https://usa.visa.com/dam/VCOM/download/visa-everywhere/global-impact/impact-of-electronic-payments-on-economic-growth.pdf>